

Stability of mitochondrial plasmidlike DNAs of rice

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B1 and B4 are small, circular plasmidlike DNAs found in rice mitochondria. We previously investigated the distribution of four kinds of plasmidlike DNA molecules in 85 *Oryza sativa* accessions (Kanazawa et al 1992). These molecules were found mostly in indicas, with a few in javanicas, and none in japonicas. Copy number also differed among the four kinds of molecules. Copy number was not conserved among cultivated rice varieties with different cytoplasms. It seems possible that mitochondrial plasmidlike DNAs could be replicated and stably maintained for at least several generations under normal environmental conditions. However, transmission of these DNAs may become irregular as a result of suppressed replication under unstable environmental conditions.

We examined whether temperature influences copy numbers of mitochondrial plasmidlike DNAs and main mitochondrial genomic DNAs, especially during cell proliferation. The observed quantitative fluctuations in levels of plasmidlike DNAs were larger and less closely related to cell proliferation than those of main mitochondrial genomic DNAs on which genes indispensable for mitochondrial biogenesis were located. The copy number of plasmidlike DNAs was reduced significantly in calli cultured at high temperatures (Fig. 1).

We developed an assay system for monitoring DNA synthesis in isolated mitochondria to examine the contribution of mtDNA replication to the quantitative fluctuations. Synthesis of the main mitochondrial genomic DNAs occurred at all the temperatures examined, whereas that of plasmidlike DNAs occurred only over a limited range of temperatures (Fig. 2). These results indicate the instability of plasmidlike DNAs relative to main mitochondrial genomic DNAs.

1. Gel blot analysis of DNAs from calli cultured at various temperatures. Total DNA (10 µg) isolated from calli cultured at 20 °C (lane 1), 25 °C (lane 2), 30 °C (lane 3), and 35 °C (lane 4) was digested with *Stu*I to linearize plasmidlike DNA, B1. After electrophoresis, the gel blot was probed with ³²P-labeled B1 and *atpA*. Signals corresponding to B1 and *atpA* are indicated on the right.

2. Gel electrophoresis of products of DNA synthesis in isolated mitochondria. MtDNAs purified from reaction mixtures incubated at 5 °C (lane 1), 13 °C (lane 2), 20 °C (lane 3), 25 °C (lane 4), 30 °C (lane 5), 35 °C (lane 6), 42 °C (lane 7), and 50 °C (lane 8) were separated on an agarose gel. After electrophoresis, the gel was placed onto an imaging plate and radioactivity was visualized and quantified using a bio-imaging analyzer. One signal of low mobility and two signals of higher mobility indicate the incorporation of labeled nucleotide into the main mitochondrial genomic DNAs and the plasmidlike DNAs, respectively.

We have detected sequences homologous to mitochondrial plasmidlike DNAs that are integrated within limited chromosomal regions on the rice nuclear genome (Kanazawa et al 1993). This suggests interorganellar sequence transfer between mitochondria and nucleus. The unstable transmission of plasmidlike DNAs shown in this study implies that plasmidlike DNA sequences have been transferred from the mitochondria to the nucleus during at least the early differentiation phase among rice varieties, before the sequences were lost from the mitochondria of some rice varieties.

Cited references

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Sensitivity of plant height genes to gibberellic acid and their regulation by endogenous plant hormones in rice

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We studied the sensitivities to gibberellic acid (GA₃) of genes governing plant height in five rice genotypes and how endogenous hormones regulate them. We also investigated proteins related to plant elongation.

Sensitivity of plant height genes to GA₃. Five rice genotypes. Er-jiu-feng (EJF, semidwarf, *sd1* gene), tall EJF (near-isogenic line [NIL] of EJF, tall *Sd1* gene), tall Zhen-shan 97 (TZS, NIL of ZS, tall, *eui* gene), Chao ai (CA, dwarf, *sdss(t)* gene), and Kyushu-3 (D53, dwarf, D53 gene) were treated with 20 and 100 mg GA₃ L⁻¹ at seedling, tillering, and heading stages. Plant elongation was measured 8 d after treatment. The sensitivities of rice genes to GA₃

1. Endogenous plant hormone contents in different rice genotypes: (a) GA₃ content (µg g⁻¹FW), (b) IAA content (nmol g⁻¹FW), (c) ZR content (pmol g⁻¹FW), (d) ABA content (nmol g⁻¹FW). GA contents of dwarf genotypes were 16.9-55.6% lower than those of tall genotypes. IAA contents were lower by 12.0-81.7% in the dwarf genotypes than in the tall genotypes. ZR and ABA contents varied among genotypes during plant growth.

2. Protein patterns in GA₃-treated and nontreated NILs. Lanes 1-6 consisted of nontreated seedlings of TEJF, EJF, TZS, ZS, 320T, and CA; lanes 7-12 consisted of TEJF, EJF, TZS, ZS, 320T, and CA seedlings treated with GA₃ for 3 d. Proteins a (about 50 kD), b (about 62 kD), c (about 50 kD), which existed in nontreated EJF, TZS, and CA, are shown with arrows; these proteins appeared in other lines of the NIL pairs after 3 d of GA₃ treatment. Another new protein d (about 52 kD) also appeared in CA. Protein standard molecular weights are shown on the left.

were found to be *ui>D53>sd1>Sd1>sds(t)* at the seedling stage. However, sensitivities of the genes changed to *D53>sd1>eui>sds(t)>Sd1* during tillering and *sd1>eui>D53>Sd1>sds(t)* during heading. The genes *eui* and *Sd1* were

classified as sensitive at all growth stages, *D53* as sensitive during seedling and tillering stages, and *Sd1* and *sds(t)* as insensitive at all stages.

Using endogenous hormones to regulate plant height genes. Plant hormones were

assayed using the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay method. More GA₃ was found in the uppermost internodes of heading plants of the tall genotypes (Fig. 1a) than in the other genotypes. Although the *eui* plants have the highest GA₃, they were highly sensitive to GA₃. The *sds(t)* plants were less sensitive to GA₃ despite their lower GA₃ content. GA₃ and indole acetic acid (IAA) were higher in the tall genotypes than in the dwarf genotypes (Fig. 1b), the highest IAA content was also found in the *eui* plants. The tall genotypes had higher zatin ribozide (ZR) content than the dwarf genotypes at seedling and tillering stages (Fig. 1c), while at heading, higher ZR contents appeared in the dwarf genotypes.

Except for the tall genotypes *Sd1* and *eui*, in which the abscisic acid (ABA) contents remained stable from the tillering stage (Fig. 1d), increases in ABA of the three dwarf genotypes began during the seedling stage. Dwarf rice plants had more ABA and less GA₃ and IAA at tillering and heading stages. Dwarf seedlings had lower ABA. Seedlings and tillering plants with low ABA were more sensitive to GA₃ than those with higher ABA. The results indicate that genes governing plant height play an important role in regulating plant hormones.

Identifying GA₃-induced proteins. According to sodium dodecylsulfate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis of seedling proteins, three proteins (Fig. 2) with molecular weights of about 50, 62, and 50 kD, existed only in the EJF (*sd1*) (a), TZS (*eui*) (b), and CA (*sds(t)*) (c) lines, respectively. After a 3-d GA₃ treatment, these proteins appeared in other lines of the NIL pairs and a new protein (d) also appeared in the CA plants. The proteins were possibly related to plant height and could have been induced by GA₃.

Hormone receptors promote the responses of plants to exogenous hormones. Genes governing plant height may take part in regulating the receptor system through some message molecules, or the receptors may induce plant height genes to affect plant elongation. In another study, we found that amounts of peroxidases and esterases differed among seedlings with different genes. ■